

BOEING 777 EMPENNAGE MANUFACTURING

Mark Iden and Doan Pham
Boeing Commercial Airplane Group
P.O. Box 3707
Seattle, Washington 98124-2207

ABSTRACT

This report describes the manufacturing processes and the facilities that are used in the fabrication of the Boeing 777 composite empennage. The Boeing 777 is the first large scale application of composites for primary structures on Boeing commercial airplanes. In support of the 777 program, The Boeing Company has invested in a facility, the Composite Manufacturing Center (CMC), located in Frederickson, Washington. The CMC is a facility laid out specifically for the fabrication of the 777 empennage. The CMC is designed to facilitate flow through manufacturing with emphasis on product lines and reduced cycle times.

The Boeing Company integrated Design/Build Teams (DBTs) in the development and manufacturing of the 777 airplane. These teams brought together organizational representatives from Engineering, Tooling, Operations Technology, Manufacturing Engineering, Quality Assurance, Manufacturing and others, with a common goal to design and build a cost effective, high quality product. These representatives came from all areas within Boeing Company. These teams working together resolved many potential problems and conflicts early in the program resulting in a smooth transition from design to fabrication. The DBT concept was also used in the planning and layout of the CMC facility, used to manufacture the 777.

The 777 empennage, as the first production application of composite primary structures on Boeing airplanes, took extensive process development. The processes developed in the laboratory environment were then transitioned to a factory built specifically around the processes and parts that were to be manufactured. The scale-up and added robustness that the processes require for cost effective composite manufacturing is a challenge that the DBTs work on extensively. The results are a world-class Composite Manufacturing Center producing a cost effective, high quality composite empennage for the Boeing 777.

1. EMPENNAGE OVERVIEW

The Composite Manufacturing Center (CMC) is a "greenfield site" that was laid out around the hardware and processes used to fabricate the 777 empennage. The 777 empennage consists of the horizontal and vertical stabilizers fabricated at the CMC. The final products produced at the CMC are the vertical fin and the left and right hand horizontal stabilizer halves. The vertical fin is shipped to the Everett, Washington 777 assembly facility ready for the installation of systems, the rudder assembly and installation onto the airplane. The stabilizer halves are shipped to the

Everett facility as separate parts and joined there. Once the stabilizers are joined, systems and the elevators are installed and the stabilizer is installed onto the airplane.

The CMC consists of both detail fabrication and assembly operations. Both were integrated along product lines to maximize process flow and minimize inventory and tooling requirements. The detail parts that the CMC produces are the main torque box components, all made of carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRP). Other detail parts, made from fiberglass, aluminum or titanium are manufactured at other existing facilities and shipped to the CMC for assembly and installation.

2. INTEGRATION

As is widely reported, Boeing utilized Design/Build Teams (DBTs) throughout the 777 program as the mechanism to ensure that the engineering, operations and the facilities organizations integrated efforts during all phases of the program. The CMC, just as the 777 as a whole, is a product of the DBT approach. Studies showed that on the fabrication of the detail parts alone, an average of 75% reduction in flow time could be realized in a dedicated product line facility versus an existing non-optimized facility. Separate teams were formed for each of the detail fabrication product lines to integrate tooling, fabrication processes, equipment and material handling systems into production product lines.

3. DETAIL FABRICATION

3.1 Product Flow and Material Handling The CMC is laid out with the lay-up/clean room and raw material freezer at one end of the facility, the autoclaves, equipped with doors on both ends, in the middle with trim and inspection at the other end. This results in a linear flow of hardware through the facility.

The clean room at the CMC utilizes Automated Guided Vehicles (AGVs) to deliver tools to the lay-up areas and once laid up, the uncured parts to the autoclave for cure. The autoclave is loaded by the AGV from the clean room side but unloaded from the debag side of the autoclave. This eliminates the "dead end" street associated with traditional autoclave installations. AGVs were chosen as the preferred material handling system in the clean room primarily due to the disruption that overhead cranes cause during lay-up operations.

3.2 Lamination The CMC utilizes Contour Tape Lamination Machines (CTLMs) for the majority of the lay-up operations. The CTLMs are used to lay-up the CFRP unidirectional tape that is used on the skin panels, stringers and miscellaneous parts. The CTLM is also equipped with an ink jet marking system that allows ply boundaries of insufficient size to machine lay cost effectively or dissimilar materials, such as fiberglass, to be hand laid up without the use of locating templates.

Charges that are used to make stringers and miscellaneous parts are laid up using the CTLM. The parts are designed such that common lay-ups are used on numerous part numbers. This allows the CTLM to lay-up charges for numerous parts at the same time thus reducing cost. The flat charges are then trimmed into individual part charges that are subsequently formed to the final part configuration.

Ribs are hand laid up using CFRP fabric material on the Hand Assist Lamination (HAL) cell. The HAL cell consists of a mechanized compaction bag and a laser projection system. The mechanized bag eliminates the time consuming operations associated with the traditional tacky

tape and nylon bag compaction process. The laser projection system eliminates the up front cost, storage and maintenance of traditional locating templates. The rib product line is an integrated cell using bar codes to order tools and download numerical control (NC) programs.

Spar fabrication was an area where late in the developmental stages of the program a fundamental process change occurred that drastically changed the manufacturing requirements. The original concept for spar fabrication was to CTLM lay a flat charge that would then be drape formed to the final configuration. However, during the drape forming operation wrinkles occurred due to the curvature of the spars.

The alternative to drape forming, hand lay-up, became the baseline manufacturing process. The challenge was to establish an integrated manufacturing sequence that would produce spars at a cost comparable to the original baseline process.

The spar process was evaluated to determine the major cost components. The process of ply location and compaction were areas determined where process improvements could be incorporated. The spar tools were then designed as hat sections on top of universal bases. The universal base allowed a mechanized bag house to be used. The use of the bag house and large vacuum lines greatly reduced the cycle time associated with compaction.

3.3 Composite Trimming All composite trimming operations are conducted on two machines, an abrasive waterjet (AWJ) gantry robot and an extrusion mill. The AWJ is used to trim skin panels, spars and the ribs. The universal trim fixture, a matrix of numerical controlled vacuum chucks has the flexibility to hold the skins, spars and ribs during the waterjet trimming operation. The minimal forces exerted by the waterjet on the part allow the universal trim fixture to work. The abrasive waterjet is also equipped with a probe head to perform dimensional inspection of parts once trimmed. This eliminates the inherent variability of trimming with one setup and/or machine and inspecting with another.

The extrusion mill is used to trim stringers and miscellaneous parts. The extrusion mill utilizes the same technology that Boeing uses to trim aluminum extrusions. The requirements of the machines were evaluated for changes that would be required to trim composites. Those required changes were then incorporated into the extrusion mills ordered for the CMC.

4. ASSEMBLY

4.1 Assembly Sequence The assembly process flow is a straight flow of parts from subassembly to major subassembly to major assembly and then to final assembly. The assembly sequence of the 777 empennage also utilizes the proven assembly concept from the 757 and 767 programs with improved modification for composite structure. The major objective is to make the composite structure cost competitive to the aluminum empennage structure.

4.2 Assembly Issues Many issues and concerns arose during the design stages of the 777 empennage. Due to the size of the 777 empennage structure and the rate requirement, some of the issues presented fresh, new challenges to resolve. Issues such as hole quality and fastener systems were unique to composite structure. Other issues such as safety/ergonomics, confined space, etc...are also applicable to metal structure. The 777 empennage assembly incorporated lessons learned from all programs within the Boeing Company.

Some of the key issues/concerns will be discussed in the next section.

4.3 Resolution of Issues and Concerns As mentioned above, many issues arose during the development stage of the 777 empennage. Some of the key issues were:

1. Hole quality
2. Safety/Ergonomics
3. Shimming
4. Fastener system

4.3.1 Hole Quality Composite drilling represents the biggest challenge in assembly. Composite materials are abrasive and can shorten drill life considerably. The quality of the hole is directly affected by the quality of the drill bit. Other problems such as fiber breakout and tight engineering tolerance on hole diameter are also a big concern.

The most common solution to fiber breakout is to have a ply of fiberglass on the drill exit side or to use fabric on the outer layer of the structure. These solutions are simple but they add weight to the structure. As a compromise (between weight and hole quality), the 777 empennage uses a new, thinner grade of fiberglass material to minimize the weight increase and prevent fiber breakout during the drilling process. However, fiberglass material also has a tendency to leave a little "fuzz" around the hole. This problem is critical to the assembly process especially for the automatic fastening machine since the parts cannot be taken apart and cleaned.

A new drill point geometry was designed and used to reduce fiberglass "fuzz". This new drill point in combination with a layer of fiberglass eliminated the fiber breakout and "fuzz" from the drilling process. This allows us to eliminate the "defuzzing" step, thus reducing the cycle time.

The 777 empennage employs different material with the major structure being CFRP composite. The fin root fittings which attach the vertical stabilizer to the tail upper deck and the pivot fittings which attach the horizontal stabilizers to the tail section are made of titanium. All hinge ribs and forward box ribs are made of aluminum. The trailing edge and forward box panels are fiberglass honeycomb sandwich structure.

All of the above materials, by themselves are a challenge to drill, but when they are stacked together in combinations present a major challenges, especially when CFRP composite and titanium are combined.

In the case of titanium/CFRP material stack (pivot fittings, fin root fittings), the new peck drilling process is used. The peck drilling process allows us to drill the Ti/Ti/CFRP/CFRP/Ti stack in one operation. The peck drilling process breaks up the titanium chips, thus minimizing the gouging problem that would occur otherwise. The peck drill process also yields tighter hole tolerances, this allows us to order drill diameters closer to the nominal hole diameter. The peck drilling process replaced the typical drill/ream process that typically is used on close tolerance holes.

Drill life is a major concern when drilling composite material. Due to the abrasive characteristics of the composite material, drill life not only affects the cost (drill replacement), but also the hole quality (hole finish). Depending on the thickness of the composite material, drill configuration and the speeds and feeds that are used, a carbide drill bit will last anywhere from a dozen holes to a hundred holes.

Poly-crystalline diamond (PCD) drills were found to be cost effective over a typical carbide drill utilizing processes developed for the 777 empennage. PCD drills lasts much longer and provides better hole quality than a typical carbide drill. PCD drills, however, are fragile, expensive and do not stand up well to side forces. On the 777 empennage program, PCD drills are used in power

feed equipment and in automated drilling machines. PCD drills in combination with a spindle with a class nine (9) bearing (on the automatic fastening machine) produce holes with variation less than measurement equipment tolerance (0.0002 inch).

Drilling in major assembly areas is done using self-collected power feed equipment. The power feed equipment utilizes the same speeds and feeds as the automatic fastening machine when drilling composite/composite material stack. The power feed equipment, however, does not have the stability that the automatic fastening machine provides. Statistical process control data indicates that the hand drilling process is not as robust as the automatic fastening machine's drilling process.

4.3.2 Safety/Ergonomics The graphite dust generated during the drilling process is a major safety issue. To eliminate graphite dust generated during the drilling operation, all power feed portable tools that are used on the 777 empennage program have a built-in dust collection attachment (DCA). The DCA reduces the amount of dust generated substantially when drilling composite materials. Test results indicated that the DCA collected approximately 90 percent of the dust generated, while the remaining 10 percent consisted of mostly heavy particulate fell to the floor immediately and is not considered to be a hazard. Dust build up also affects hole quality and reduces drill life. A major challenge was to develop a DCA that can be adapted to different equipment set-ups.

To have an effective, ergonomically designed tool, the Tool Designer must consider and incorporate ergonomics into the design. On the 777 empennage program, Manufacturing through the Design Build Team (DBT) had the opportunity to voice their concerns. Not only production supervisors but also lead mechanics were members of the DBTs. Their experiences on the assembly line ensured that all tools were designed and built around the operator.

The goal was to minimize bending, lifting and fatigue. As a result, the subassembly area has Assembly Jigs (A.J.) that rotate. All operations in the major assembly (first stage) can be performed in an optimum position (chest level). The major assembly (second stage) also has multiple work platforms to reduce bending and reaching.

4.3.3 Shimming Shimming was a major issue that required extensive development for the 777 empennage program. Uneven surfaces associated with the bag side of the parts needed to be addressed, these surfaces included spar flanges, skin panel interface and the areas between the fin root fittings and the vertical stabilizer skin panels.

Improved moldable plastic shimming (MPS) was the solution since it has the filling properties which improve joint performance.

4.3.4 Fastener System During the planning stages of the program, a single fastener system (excluding rivet and removable fastener) was proposed as a method to reduce fastener cost and inventory. However, due to the limited versatility and robustness of any one fastener system, a single fastener system was not implemented.

The 777 empennage employs several fastener systems. The two major fastener systems are the Lokbolt design from Huck and the Eddie-bolt2 design from Voi-Shan/Fairchild. Stump Lokbolts are used in automatic fastening machines and pull type Lokbolts for manual installation. Eddie-bolt2 is also used in manual application but only in limited access areas or where faying surface seal or wet installation of fasteners are required. In areas where fastener diameters are larger than 3/8 inch, Hi-Lok fasteners are used.

During production start-up, the flexibility of more than one fastener system allows manufacturing to compare and determine which fastener system works best for a particular application. This also allows manufacturing to substitute one fastener system for another as availability issues arise. This supports the decision to use more than one fastener system.

5. CONCLUSION

The 777 composite empennage required extensive process development early in the program to assure the processes were well defined. The defined processes were used to layout a product flow integrating processes, equipment and material handling systems.

The effective organizational teaming (DBTs) and employee's efforts to reduce costs were the keys which made the 777 empennage one of the most successful start-up programs at The Boeing Company. Also contributing to the success of the program, but not to be overlooked, was the effective adaptation of lessons learned from other programs, effective use of automation and management support in eliminating roadblocks.

The 777 empennage program is well on its way of reducing the cost normally associated with lightweight high performance composite material.

6. BIOGRAPHIES

Mark Iden is a Specialist Engineer, Composite Manufacturing Center support, in the Operations Technology organization. He received his Bachelor Degree (1985) in Manufacturing Engineering Technology from Western Washington University. Mr. Iden has worked on primary structure composite applications at The Boeing Company for nine (9) years.

Doan Pham is a Senior Specialist Engineer, Composite Manufacturing Center support, in the Operations Technology organization. He received his Bachelor Degree (1982) in Mechanical Engineering from the University of Oklahoma and his Master in Business Administration (1987) from California State Polytechnic University, Pomona. Mr. Pham has been on the 777 empennage program since the program kick off.